

Multicarrier Transmission Optimization in Elastic Optical Networks

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the trade-off between Quality of Transmission (QoT) performance and spectrum efficiency through low-margin operation of multicarriers. Margin reduction is enabled by implementing tight filtering and slight subcarriers overlap. Experiments conducted on a Software Defined Networking (SDN)-controlled Elastic Optical Network (EON) testbed demonstrate spectrum-efficient multicarriers composed of three subcarriers, achieving savings of up to 22% in spectrum occupation for 80 km optical connections.

Keywords: multicarrier transmission, spectrum optimization, reduced transmission margins, SDN control

1. INTRODUCTION

Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) [1] have been developed for high spectral efficiency to maximize fiber use. Furthermore, coherent technology and utilization of various modulation formats help balance spectral efficiency with optical reach. Diverse traffic requirements (i.e., different bit rates and bandwidths) accommodated by the EONs through the ITU-T flexible grid [2] allow for configurable channel slot widths. Therefore, multicarrier (or super-channel) transmission, enabled by this flexibility, is one of the most suitable solutions for supporting ever-increasing traffic rate [3]. However, multicarrier spectrum optimization is challenging due to the filtering effects and subcarrier cross-talk [3-5] that result in the overall quality of transmission (QoT) degradation.

Traditionally, optical network design has been mainly driven by the traffic increase, leading to overprovisioning for capacity, physical-layer conditions, and modelling uncertainties (e.g., equipment aging) to ensure long-term reliability (e.g., several years) [3, 6-8]. Therefore, reduced margin operation, which involves approaching the minimum performance threshold (e.g., the pre-forward error correction (FEC)-bit error rate (BER) threshold), could improve network efficiency and reduce costs without compromising reliability. However, in the context of low-margin operation, network automation and monitoring of the physical-layer parameters is crucial to react against critical performance degradation [8].

Software defined networking (SDN) architecture has enabled vendor-neutral control of optical networks by disaggregating network devices into two logical sections: the data plane representing the physical infrastructure and the control plane responsible for network configuration and management [9]. The SDN controller maintains a complete network view and communicates with network devices through local agents leveraging dedicated protocols. NETCONF [10], enabled by YANG modelling language [11] responsible for describing the underlying infrastructure, is a standard protocol considered for the SDN implementation in optical networks.

The OpenConfig YANG model [11] characterizes the main parameters of optical transponders and enables the configuration (e.g., frequency, target output power) and monitoring (e.g., pre-FEC-BER) by utilizing NETCONF protocol. Furthermore, vendor-specific parameters, such as modulation format, FEC, and bit rate, are abstracted and exposed to the SDN controller as attributes called operational (OP) modes, thus enabling the model to remain stable regardless of the advanced proprietary transmission solutions.

Typically, the SDN controller is responsible for configuring optical channel parameters (e.g., OP mode) and wavelength selective switches (WSSs) parameters (e.g., switched bandwidth) for individual optical channels. However, when addressing multicarrier transmission, this strategy may encounter scalability challenges due to the multiple iterations required by the SDN controller to fine-tune the subcarrier spacing for maximizing spectrum savings. In contrast, the proposed multicarrier spectrum saving optimization in [3] is performed directly by the local NETCONF agents, therefore reducing the SDN controller involvement in the spectrum optimization procedure significantly.

In this paper, utilizing the methodology outlined in [3], we experimentally demonstrate low-margin operation for multicarriers composed of three subcarriers to optimize spectrum efficiency. Reduced margin transmission is achieved by allowing subcarriers to slightly overlap and introducing tight filtering at the side subcarriers. Therefore, system performance is allowed to get closer to the QoT threshold, thus enabling spectrum savings. The optimization procedure does not involve the SDN controller for fine tuning the subcarrier spacing, it is rather performed by the NETCONF local agents at the transceivers. Experimental demonstration is carried out considering the optical reach of 80 km and leveraging 600 Gbit/s transponder supporting OpenConfig OP modes. The experiments show that up to 22% of the spectrum savings per multicarrier could be achieved by utilizing the proposed reduced margin operation.

2. METHOD

The proposed optimization procedure for spectrum-efficient multicarrier transmission is described in this section. The procedure considers transmission of three subcarriers and leverages OpenConfig YANG model for the subcarrier (re-)configuration (i.e., central frequency and OP mode selection) and pre-FEC-BER monitoring. Transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) subcarrier central frequencies are moved in steps of 6.25 GHz (i.e., according to the ITU-T flex grid) towards either left or right filter border to allow for tight filtering and slight subcarrier overlap. Then, the pre-FEC-BER degradation resulting from low-margin operation is continuously monitored to ensure sufficient QoT.

Figure 1. Multicarrier Spectrum Saving Optimization Procedure

To define multicarrier spectrum savings, let us first consider the subcarriers adjacent to the filter borders. For example, the bandwidth saving of the left-hand subcarrier is defined as an (x, y) pair, where x represents multiple of 6.25 GHz slots saved from the filter side, while y indicates the savings enabled by the overlap with the middle subcarrier. When the central frequencies of the adjacent subcarriers move closer to one another (i.e., overlapping the signals), the spectrum saving resulting from this slight overlap must be symmetrical. Thus, the bandwidth saving for the middle subcarrier is defined as a (y, z) pair, where y and z indicate overlaps with left-hand and right-hand subcarriers, respectively. Finally, (z, w) represents the savings from right-hand subcarrier. Therefore, the nominal spectrum occupation could be reduced by a sum of (x, y, y, z, z, w) values, each representing a multiple of 6.25 GHz, as illustrated in Fig. 1. For example, $(2, 1, 1, 0, 0, 3)$ saving indicates that: (1) the left-hand sub-carrier has been moved two 6.25 GHz steps closer to the left filter border, (2) the left-hand and the middle subcarriers overlap, saving one 6.25 GHz slot per subcarrier, (3) the middle and the right-hand subcarriers do not overlap, and finally (4) three slots are saved from the right filter border. Therefore, this results in a total of 43.75 GHz of saved spectrum.

Furthermore, the maximum acceptable bandwidth saving for the subcarriers next to the filter borders is three steps of 6.25 GHz. There are different (x, y) combinations that can achieve such saving, e.g., $(3, 0)$ or $(2, 1)$ for the left-hand subcarrier. On the other hand, for the middle subcarriers, $(1, 1)$ saving corresponding to (y, z) pair is the only possible option enabling the maximum spectrum reduction (i.e., two 6.25 GHz slots). However, it is important to note that no additional spectrum can be saved from the middle subcarrier if the $(3, 0)$ saving is applied to the left-hand subcarrier, as there would be no overlap between the subcarriers.

The network reference scenario in Fig. 2 (a) shows the SDN controller, Tx, Rx, and WSS NETCONF agents. The Tx agent, composed of the OpenConfig Tx agent and the optimization agent, is responsible for applying the

Figure 2. (a) Network Reference Scenario; (b) NETCONF message exchange for provisioning, reconfiguration, and monitoring

low-margin operation. The OpenConfig Rx agent is utilized for QoT (i.e., pre-FEC-BER) monitoring. Fig. 2 (b) describes the exchange of NETCONF control messages for the initial provisioning, and (re-)configuration and monitoring during the optimization procedure. Initially, the SDN controller configures subcarriers by setting their Tx/Rx central frequencies, target output power and OP modes. It also configures WSSs along the optical path by reserving the nominal bandwidth resources (i.e., at least 225 GHz of spectrum for three 75 GHz subcarriers) as shown in the first step of Fig. 1. Then, the SDN controller communicates with the Tx agent via REST API (Fig. 2 (b) step 1), thus initiating the optimization procedure.

In [3], two different procedures for multicarriers composed of two subcarriers are outlined: (1) homogeneous spectrum saving procedure for the transmission of the same OP mode subcarriers, and (2) hybrid procedure for optimizing subcarriers of different OP modes. However, when addressing multicarrier transmission involving more than two subcarriers, the procedure does not differentiate between different multicarrier types. Moreover, in [3], the optimization procedure starts by investigating all possible spectrum saving combinations corresponding to the maximum acceptable saving, i.e., (3, 0), (2, 1), (1, 2), and (0, 3). The optimal solution is then obtained based on the best acceptable pre-FEC-BER. In this work, the Tx optimization agent aims to maximize spectrum savings by initially optimizing both the left-hand and middle subcarriers simultaneously, applying (2, 1) and (1, 1) savings, respectively. The subcarriers reconfiguration is enforced leveraging NETCONF <edit-config> messages. Furthermore, NETCONF <get> messages for monitoring QoT parameters are utilized to determine whether the savings are supported by the subcarriers (i.e., acceptable pre-FEC-BER).

The pre-FEC-BER monitoring is critical for finding an optimal solution. First, the procedure monitors the pre-FEC-BER values of the left-hand subcarrier for the applied saving. If the configuration is suitable (i.e., pre-FEC-BER value is lower than the pre-determined threshold (TH) to guarantee error-free transmission), the procedure then starts monitoring the middle subcarrier. Otherwise, the procedure then considers a lower spectrum saving configuration [e.g., (1, 1) setting] and reconfigures the middle optical channel accordingly. Once the left-hand subcarrier is optimized, if the pre-FEC-BER value of the middle channel is above the given TH, the procedure similarly applies a lower spectrum saving to optimize it. However, reconfiguring the middle subcarrier might affect the left-hand subcarrier as well. For example, let us consider (2, 1) configuration setting for the left-hand channel, while the middle channel is monitored for (1, 0) configuration. If the pre-FEC-BER of the middle subcarrier is above TH, (0, 0) configuration is attempted (i.e., there is no subcarrier overlap from either adjacent sides). However, the left-hand subcarrier needs to be reconfigured accordingly to (3, 0) saving configuration to maintain the previous spectrum saving. Finally, once the first two subcarriers are optimized (i.e., Fig. 1 step 2), the procedure then moves all channels towards the right filter border to optimize the right-hand subcarrier saving from the filter side, as demonstrated in Fig.1 step 3. For instance, if the configuration before shifting is (2, 0, 0, 1, 1, w), the w value could be 2, 1, or 0. The optimization procedure aims to maximize spectrum savings by attempting to save two slots from the right-hand filter border. However, if this configuration is unfeasible (pre-FEC-BER > TH), the procedure explores lower spectrum saving options. Finally, the SDN controller reconfigures the filter enforcing the optimal spectrum occupation, as shown in Fig. 1 step 4.

3. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND RESULTS

The multicarrier optimization experiments have been conducted using the testbed shown at the bottom of Fig. 2 (a). Three optical channels are aggregated at the Tx side before passing through the first WSS and the first amplifier to ensure an optical power of 0 dBm per subcarrier. The subcarriers then traverse an 80 km fiber span,

Table 1. Results of the spectrum saving optimization procedure according to the OP mode combination for an 80 km optical connection

Total Bit Rate	Nominal Bandwidth	Multicarrier	Modulation Format	Bit rate	Pre-FEC-BER	Saving	Optimized Bandwidth
1500 Gbit/s	225 GHz	OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.33E-2	(1,1,1,0,0,2)	193.75 GHz
		OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.14E-2		
		OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.36E-2		
600 Gbit/s	225 GHz	OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	3.37E-5	(2,1,1,1,1,2)	175 GHz
		OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	5.65E-6		
		OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	8.02E-4		
1100 Gbit/s	225 GHz	OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.13E-2	(1,1,1,1,1,2)	181.25 GHz
		OP3	DP-16QAM	400 Gbit/s	2.46E-2		
		OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	3.88E-3		
1100 Gbit/s	225 GHz	OP3	DP-16QAM	400 Gbit/s	1.76E-2	(1,1,1,0,0,3)	187.5 GHz
		OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.04E-2		
		OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	1.75E-3		
1100 Gbit/s	225 GHz	OP2	DP-32QAM	500 Gbit/s	2.09E-2	(1,1,1,1,1,1)	187.5 GHz
		OP6	8PSK	200 Gbit/s	3.30E-4		
		OP3	DP-16QAM	400 Gbit/s	2.08E-2		

pass through a second WSS and another amplifier, and finally reach their respective Rx.

Results of the spectrum saving optimization procedure for multicarrier transmission, and details on the single subcarrier OP modes (i.e., bit rate and modulation format) are reported in Table 1. For example, 400 Gbit/s and DP-16QAM correspond to a single OP3 subcarrier. Moreover, the nominal spectrum occupation for each considered OP mode is 75 GHz. Therefore, to transmit 1.5 THz three OP2 subcarriers are utilized, and 225 GHz of spectrum is reserved. The spectrum saving configuration and corresponding pre-FEC-BER values are reported. For instance, in case of transmitting three OP6 subcarriers, 50 GHz (22.22%) of occupied bandwidth is saved by applying (2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2) configuration.

Moreover, two multicarrier types are considered: homogeneous, consisting of the same OP mode subcarriers, and hybrid, composed of subcarriers presenting different OP modes. An example of a homogeneous multicarrier transmission is a combination of three OP6 subcarriers. On the other hand, OP2 OP3 OP6 represents an instance of a hybrid transmission. Unlike reported in [3], spectrum saving procedure is not necessarily symmetrical when considering homogeneous multicarriers. Such example is the transmission of three OP2 subcarriers, where (1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 2) saving combination is applied to enable 31.25 GHz (13.88%) of spectrum. This is due to the impact of the cross-talk on the pre-FEC-BER degradation as reported in [3]. Therefore, considering the advanced modulation format of OP2 (i.e., DP-32QAM), the pre-FEC-BER of the middle channel approaches the experimentally obtained TH of $2.5E-2$ faster, even with just one slot saved.

Three hybrid multicarriers capable of transmitting 1.1 THz, that are composed of different combinations of OP2, OP3 and OP6 subcarriers are reported in Table 1. It is important to note that the selection of the proper OP mode for the middle channel affects the multicarrier performance in terms of optimized spectrum occupation. For example, the most spectrum efficient subcarrier combination is OP2 OP3 OP6 allowing for the 43.75 GHz (19.44%) of bandwidth to be saved. However, one less spectrum slot could be saved if OP2 is considered as a middle subcarrier, thus affecting the overall spectrum performance. Similarly, configuring the middle subcarrier to OP6 prevents taking advantage of its robustness, leading to reduced spectrum saving compared to utilizing OP6 adjacent to the filter borders. Therefore, careful consideration of OP mode selection for middle subcarriers is necessary. This is particularly important when increasing the optical reach. For example, OP2 becomes unavailable for spectrum saving when traversing 320 km [3], thus OP2 as the middle channel would allow other OP modes next to the filter borders to attribute to the total bandwidth reduction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Spectrum saving optimization procedure for multicarrier transmission is experimentally demonstrated in an EON testbed. The proposed procedure allows for the spectrum reduction of up to 22% when considering the transmission of three subcarriers of various OP modes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Chatterjee and E. Oki, *Elastic Optical Networks: Fundamentals, Design Control, and Management* (2020).
- [2] <https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx?recD14498>.
- [3] M. Radovic, A. Sgambelluri, F. Cugini, et al., "Super-channel spectrum saving optimization procedure in elastic optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 15, 68–77 (2023).
- [4] A. P. Vela, M. Ruiz, F. Fresi, N. Sambo, F. Cugini, G. Meloni, L. Potì, L. Velasco, and P. Castoldi, "BER degradation detection and failure identification in elastic optical networks," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 35, 4595–4604 (2017).
- [5] J. M. Fabrega, M. S. Moreolo, L. Martín, A. Chiadò Piat, E. Riccardi, D. Roccatò, N. Sambo, F. Cugini, L. Potì, S. Yan, and E. Hugues-Salas, "On the filter narrowing issues in elastic optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 8, A23–A33 (2016).
- [6] Y. Pointurier, "Design of low-margin optical networks," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 9, A9–A17 (2017).
- [7] J.-L. Augé, "Can we use flexible transponders to reduce margins?" in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference/National Fiber Optic Engineers Conference (OFC/NFOEC)* (2013), paper OTu2A.1.
- [8] K. Christodouloupoulos, C. Delezoide, N. Sambo, A. Kretsis, I. Sartzetakis, A. Sgambelluri, N. Argyris, G. Kanakis, P. Giardina, G. Bernini, and D. Roccatò, "Toward efficient, reliable, and autonomous optical networks: the ORCHESTRA solution [Invited]," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 11, 9, C10–C24 (2019).

- [9] N. Andriolli, A. Giorgetti, P. Castoldi, G. Cecchetti, I. Cerutti, N. Sambo, A. Sgambelluri, L. Valcarengi, F. Cugini, B. Martini, and F. Paolucci, “Optical networks management and control: a review and recent challenges,” *Opt. Switching Netw.* 44, 100652 (2022).
- [10] R. Enns, M. Bjorklund, J. Schoenwaelder, and A. Bierman, eds., “Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF),” IETF RFC 6241 (2011).
- [11] M. Bjorklund, ed., “YANG—A Data Modeling Language for the Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF),” IETF RFC 6020 (2010).
- [12] <https://www.openconfig.net/>.